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Normal Conducting Magnets - Case Study

Design of MEBT dipole magnets for MedAustron

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1 Introduction

MedAustron is a large-scale facility in Austria, that is employed for medical treatment and non-clinical research (the layout of the instrument is presented in Figure 1). It consists of a synchrotron with a circumference of 76m, and four irradiation lines. Both protons and C^{6+} ions are accelerated for different energies (usually in the MeV region) in this facility. The objective in this exercise is to analytically and numerically design and optimise three identical dipoles to be installed in the MEBT (Medium-Energy Transport Line) between the LINAC and the synchrotron.

Figure 1: This figure shows the schematic of the MedAustron facility in Austria.

The parameters of the beam transported by the MEBT line is given in Table 1 and the required magnet specifications and limitations are provided in Table 2. These specifications must be obtained through the choice and design of the magnet and can be further optimised numerically with FEMM simulations.

Table 1: Beam parameters

Parameter	Value
Particle type	Protons, C^{6+}
Beam energy	7 MeV/u
Length of beam line	40.9 m
Beta function β_x, β_y	≈ 10 m
Beam size σ_x, σ_y	± 10 mm
Margin for closed orbit distortions	± 10 mm

Table 2: Functional specifications

Parameter	Value
Number of magnets	3 (+1)
Bending angle (per magnet)	36 deg
Max. mechanical length per magnet (l_{mech})	0.9 m
Horizontal good-field region	± 30 mm
Vertical good-field region	± 23 mm
Field quality inside GFR ($\Delta B/B$)	$< \pm 1 \times 10^{-3}$
Available cooling water pressure (P_{in})	10 bar
Required return pressure (P_{out})	2 bar
Inlet water temperature (T_{in})	20°C
Max. temperature increase on magnet (ΔT)	15°C
Max. converter current	600 A
Max. converter voltage (3 magnets in series)	100 V

1.1 Additional constraints

The magnet operates in quasi-static mode. However, the magnet yokes must be constructed from laminated steel already available in stock (type M1200-100A). Only a single power converter is accessible, necessitating the electrical connection of the three magnets in series. Additionally, a complete spare unit will be necessary. If feasible (to be decided in the analysis), one of the following copper conductors from available stock should be utilised (See Table 3).

Table 3: Conductor Specifications

Conductor type	Copper grade	Outer dimensions	Diameter of cooling duct	Edge rounding radius	Available length
Type 1	OF-Cu	25 mm \times 25 mm	12 mm	1.5 mm	≈ 300 m
Type 2	OF-Cu	11 mm \times 11 mm	5.5 mm	1 mm	≈ 600 m
Type 3	OF-Cu	11 mm \times 11 mm	5 mm	1 mm	≈ 800 m
Type 4	OF-Cu	8 mm \times 8 mm	5 mm	1 mm	≈ 500 m

2 Beam parameters

In order to determine the magnetic field needed for the dipole to transport both proton and carbon ion beams from the LINAC to the synchrotron, we have to calculate the beam rigidity of both

beams using the following formula,

$$B\rho = \frac{1}{qc} \sqrt{E_{kin}^2 + 2E_{kin}E_0}. \quad (1)$$

The beam passing through the MEBT line has an energy of 7 MeV/u, which gives a total kinetic energy of 7 MeV and 84 MeV for protons and carbon ions, respectively. The beam rigidity for protons and carbon ions were found to be $B\rho_p = 0.352$ Tm for the proton beam and $B\rho_{C^{6+}} = 0.704$ Tm for the carbon beam. Since the carbon ion beam is more rigid than the proton beam, we designed and optimised the magnet to be operable with the carbon ion beam.

3 Analytical design: magnet parameters

For the design of our magnet, we chose a straight magnet since these magnets are easier to produce with laminated steel. The overhead in material compared to a straight magnet is estimated to be lower than the additional production cost for bending the magnet. Further, we will design a H shape magnet, since this magnet needs less material, and leads to a symmetric field with shielding of the field lines.

The aperture height of the magnet can be calculated from the vertical good field region, including the vacuum and insulation thickness and some tolerance for installation. The estimates for these parameters are given in table 4 and the aperture height of the magnet was determined to be $h = 0.054$ m.

Table 4: Parameters used for the calculation of the aperture height

Parameter	Value (m)
VGFR	0.023
tolerances	0.002
insulation thickness	0.001
vacuum thickness	0.001

With an optimised yoke length of $l_{yoke} = 0.63$ m, such that the available mechanical length of 0.9m is fully used, the effective length is $l_{eff} = l_{yoke} + h = 0.684$ m. Given the dipole bending angle of 36° , the bending radius ρ was found to be 1.089 m, with a maximal field of $B = 0.704$ T for the carbon ions.

The pole width for an optimised pole can be calculated from the following formulae,

$$W_p = 2(HGFR + x_p) \quad (2)$$

$$x_{p,opt} = \frac{h}{2} \left(-0.14 \log \frac{\Delta B}{B} - 0.25 \right), \quad (3)$$

and is found to be $W_p = 0.099\text{m}$ for a field quality of $\frac{\Delta B}{B} = 10^{-3}$. For a straight magnet, the sagitta can be calculated from the following formula,

$$s = \rho \left(1 - \cos \frac{\theta}{2} \right), \quad (4)$$

and is determined to be $s = 0.053\text{m}$. The total pole width including the sagitta is then $W_p = 0.152\text{m}$.

In order to avoid saturation, a maximal field of 1.3T in the yoke legs was assumed. Since only half of the flux in the gap has to pass through the leg, the leg width (return yoke thickness) can be determined from

$$W_{leg} = \frac{B_{gap}/2}{B_{leg}} (W_p + 2h) \quad (5)$$

and a leg width of $W_{leg} = 0.070\text{ m}$ was found.

Figure 2: Image taken from the slides about normal conducting magnets of Thomas Zickler.

In order to produce the desired field on the magnet, we calculated the excitation current, NI , using

$$NI \approx \frac{Bh}{2\eta\mu_0} = 15\,433 \text{ Ampere-turns}. \quad (6)$$

where η is the magnetic efficiency of the iron yoke which is assumed to be 0.98.

Since the three magnets are connected in series with a maximum converter current of 600 A , we first determined the number of turns needed around the pole in order to reach the desired field while having less than 90% of the maximum converter current for operational safety and reliability. The number of turns was approximated to be 32 with a 4x8 configuration as presented in Fig. 3a and the nominal current was determined to be 482.29 A .

Since there are different conductors available for creating the magnet coil, we decided the type of conductor based on the current density of the conductor which can be calculated by determining the conductor area (white part) shown in Fig. 3b and the available length of the conductor. The total conductor area of the different conductor types are presented in Table 5.

Figure 3: Schematic diagram of the coil geometry and conductor area.

Table 5: Total conductor area of the different conductor types.

Conductor type	Outer area [mm ²]	Edge rounding area [mm ²]	Cooling duct area [mm ²]	Total conductor area [mm ²]
Type 1	625	1.93	113.10	509.971 247 9
Type 2	121	0.86	23.76	96.383 298 21
Type 3	121	0.86	19.63	100.506 638 6
Type 4	64	0.86	19.63	43.506 638 57

For this magnet design, both type 2 and type 3 conductor are suitable due to their current densities which are around 5 A/mm² and the size of their cooling ducts which are directly related to the constraints on the cooling system. The average length of the coil was calculated to be 1.96 m, which results in a total conductor length per coil of around 62.6 m. In order to justify the choice of conductor type, we calculate the resistance $R(T)$, voltage drop U and power dissipated P_Ω using the nominal current in the coil through the following equations:

$$R(T_0) = \frac{Nl_{avg}}{a_c \sigma} \quad (7)$$

$$R(T) = R(T_0)(1 + \alpha(T_{avg} - T_0)) \quad (8)$$

$$U = RI \quad (9)$$

$$P_\Omega = UI = RI^2 \quad (10)$$

The calculated values for these parameters are presented in Table 6. Knowing these values, we could calculate for the required cooling in order to keep the system stable and operable.

Table 6: Calculated values for resistance $R(T)$, voltage drop U and power dissipated P_Ω in the coil.

Parameter	Type 2	Type 3
coil resistance [m Ω]	11.53	11.06
voltage drop [V]	5.56	5.33
power dissipated [kW]	2.68	2.57

Lastly, for the design of the cooling system, the type of cooling system was decided depending of the current density of the coil. Due to the obtained current densities of both coil types which were between $3 \text{ A/mm}^2 \leq J_c \leq 10 \text{ A/mm}^2$, we needed to use direct water cooling which required us to calculate the water flow Q , the average water velocity v_{avg} , the pressure drop ΔP , and the Reynolds number Re . These parameters were calculated using the following formulas

$$Q = 14.5 \frac{P_\Omega}{\Delta T} \quad (11)$$

$$v_{avg} = 66.67 \frac{Q}{d_h^2 \pi} \quad (12)$$

$$\Delta P = 53.32 \frac{Q^{1.75}}{d_h^{4.75}} l_h \quad (13)$$

$$Re = \frac{v_{avg} d_h}{\nu} \quad (14)$$

where P_Ω is the dissipated power, d_h is the hydraulic diameter, l_h is the cooling circuit length, and ν is the kinematic viscosity of coolant which is assumed to be constant ($6.58 \times 10^{-7} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$). The calculated values for the cooling parameters needed for both carbon ions and protons are provided in Table 7.

Table 7: Calculated values for the cooling system parameters.

Parameter	Type 2 (C^{6+}/p)	Type 3 (C^{6+}/p)
working temperature [$^\circ C$]	27.5	27.5
water flow [litre/min]	2.59/0.65	2.49/0.62
average water velocity [m/s]	1.82/0.45	2.11/0.53
pressure drop [bar]	5.38/0.48	7.86/0.69
Reynolds number	15 202.91/3 798.11	16 037.12/4 006.52

Comparing the obtained values to the constraints provided for the magnet design and operation, both conductor types fit within the limits and therefore can be used for the design of the magnet. The pressure drops for both carbon ion and proton beam are within the 8 bar limit. However, if we try to look at the Reynolds number, which is a quantity that helps predict the fluid flow pattern and

is recommended to be $Re > 4000$ in order to have turbulent flow, only the type 3 conductor achieves this constraint for both carbon ion and proton beam without changing the working temperature of the magnet. Therefore, for the final design of the dipole magnet, we decided to use the type 3 conductor for the coil design. A summary of the chosen design parameters for the dipole magnet are presented in Table 8.

Table 8: Summary of the important design parameters of the dipole magnet

Important design parameters			
Total mechanical length [m]	0.90	Horizontal good field region (HGFR) + Sagitta	0.06
Magnet type	Straight	Coil width [m]	0.10
Magnet shape	H-shape	Coil height [m]	0.05
Aperture height [m]	0.05	Insulation thickness between conductors [m]	0.001
Yoke length [m]	0.63	Insulation thickness outside [m]	0.003
Effective yoke length [m]	0.68	Total conductor length per coil [m]	62.61
Flux density B [T] (C^{6+}/p)	0.70/0.35	Total conductor length per magnet [m]	125.23
Pole width [m]	0.15	Total conductor length for 4 magnets [m]	500.90
Return yoke thickness [m]	0.07	Coil resistance $R(T=27.5^\circ C)$ [Ω] (C^{6+}/p)	0.01/0.01
Excitation current [ampere-turns] (C^{6+}/p)	15433.13/7713.19	Voltage drop [V] (C^{6+}/p)	5.33/2.67
Coil cooling	direct water cooling	Power dissipated [kW] (C^{6+}/p)	2.57/0.64
Nominal current [I] (C^{6+}/p)	482.29/241.06	Water flow Q [litre/min] (C^{6+}/p)	2.49/0.62
Number of turns	32	Average water velocity [m/s] (C^{6+}/p)	2.11/0.53
Conductor dimensions	type 3	Pressure drop ΔP [bar]	7.86/0.69
Current density [A/mm ²] (C^{6+}/p)	4.80/2.40	Reynolds number Re (C^{6+}/p)	16037.12/4006.52

4 Numerical design: results and optimised pole profile

The numerical design is done with the software FEMM 4.2. To save time and be more efficient, we are designing only one-fourth of the magnet thanks to the symmetry. We can assign each block a material and a size mesh. We apply the boundary conditions to our model, we use the Dirichlet condition to have no magnetic flux through the yoke edges. The unoptimised design result can be seen in Figure 4.

Figure 4: This figure shows the unoptimised numerical design of the proposed magnet.

After our first unoptimised shape results, we can see that we could optimise the shape of the Yoke to avoid some saturation regions and to save some steel where there is no magnetic field in the yoke (See Figure 5).

Figure 5: This figure shows the optimised numerical design of the proposed magnet.

The pole profile was optimised by adding material (steel) onto the pole to manipulate the shape of the magnetic field profile in the gap of the magnet. A closer look on the pole shimming is shown in Fig. 6.

Figure 6: Optimised pole profile shimming.

Using the optimised numerical design (in FEMM), we derived the magnetic field pattern generated by our design and compared it to the optimised design, as depicted in Figure 7a. Notably, the reference point "0" denotes the centre of the good field region (GFR), with the magnetic field profile plotted against the distance from this centre to one end in a single direction. Symmetric behaviour is observed in the opposite direction. Within a range of up to 56.6 mm along the horizontal axis

(including the good field region and sagitta), for both Carbon ions (0.704 T) and Protons (0.352 T) the designed magnet exhibited an almost uniform magnetic field. These findings align closely with the values calculated during the analytical design phase (Section 3).

Figure 7: Optimisation of the pole profile to obtain desired field in the good field region (GFR).

In addition, we also took a closer look at the dB/B_0 in the GFR which are presented in the Fig. 7b. Changing the pole profile greatly improved the dB/B_0 such that most of the GFR are within $\pm 1 \times 10^{-3}$, however further improvements on the optimisation can still be performed.

5 Cost estimation

Now that we have an optimised shape, we can estimate the cost for three magnets and one spare magnet. Firstly, we are going to compute the cost of building these four magnets. Then, we will estimate the running costs for 20 years of operations, assuming that the price of electricity will stay constant. We can find the various prices used in Table 9.

Table 9: Cost and Pricing Data

Item	Cost/Rate
Design	10 000 €
Stamping tool	15 000 €
Stacking tool	12 000 €
Winding tool	10 000 €
Impregnation mould	15 000 €
Steel	1.5 €/kg
Copper conductor	18 €/kg
Yoke manufacturing	12 €/kg
Coil manufacturing	36 €/kg
Auxiliary parts (per magnet)	5 000 €
Electricity	95 €/MWh
Operation hours	4 200 hrs/year

To start our estimation, we can compute the weight of steel needed for the yoke as we can see in Table 10.

Table 10: Yoke price estimation

Volume of 4 Yokes	0.187 m^3
Density of steel	7 850 kg/m^3
Weight of 4 Yokes	1 470 kg
Total price to buy Steel	2 205 €
Price to manufacture the Yokes	17 640 €

Now, we can compute the price of copper and for coil manufacturing as shown in Table 11.

Table 11: Coil price estimation

Volume of one copper conductor	0.000 119 665 m^3
Total number of conductors	256
Density of copper	8 940 kg/m^3
Weight of conductors	450 kg
Total price to buy Copper	8 101 €
Price to manufacture the Coils	16 202 €

We can see that even if the quantity of copper is lower than the quantity of steel needed, the

price of copper has a large effect on the costs. If there was a need to reduce the costs, it would be efficient to try to reduce the volume of copper. To be more precise, we could add the price of the insulator.

To finish the manufacturing, we need to add the design, the stamping tool, the stacking tool, the winding tool, the impregnation mould, and the auxiliary parts (20 000 € in total) from Table 9. This leads us to a price of 126 149 € for the manufacturing.

Now we are ready to compute the running costs for three magnets, with protons for 60% of the time and carbon ions for 40% in table 12.

Table 12: Operating costs for 20 years

	Protons	Carbon ion
Power (kW)	3.855	15.431 4
Hours of operation	50 400	33 600
Total price of electricity	18 457.740 €	49 557.029 €

Table 13: Total price estimation

Manufacturing	126 149 €
Operating	67 714 €
Total	193 863 €

In table 13, we find a price of 193 863 euros, which is of course an estimation because the price of electricity will probably evolve in 20 years.

When comparing the results with C-shape magnets from other groups, we found that our total cost is much lower than for C-shape magnets. This brings another reason to choose H-shape.

6 Conclusion

To conclude, we were able to design optimised magnets for MedAustron. The design respects all the constraints given by the facility.

Both protons and carbon ion beams can be used, with a beam rigidity of $B\rho = 0.704 \text{ Tm}$ for the most rigid beam (the carbon ion beam). The magnets will be straight and H-shaped. We computed the different yoke dimensions.

We found 15 433 Ampere-turns, a nominal current of 482 A and a conductor length per coil of 62.6 m. The conductor type 3 was chosen to have a turbulent flow for the cooling system.

Thanks to the numerical simulation, the shape of the yoke was optimised and we were able to reduce the volume of steel and we also reduced the magnetic saturation of the yoke.

To finish, we estimated the costs of building the 4 magnets and the operating costs over 20 years to be 193 863 euros. Our constant optimisation of the design during this study led to a visible optimisation of the costs.